

Groundwater Quality Assessment around Nagalkeni Tannery Industrial Belt

Authors : D. SIVAKUMAR

Abstract : The groundwater quality was assessed nearby places of Nagalkeni, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. The selected physico-chemical parameters were pH, EC, TDS, total hardness (TH), anions like Ca, Mg, Na and K, and cations like SO₄, NO₃, Cl₂, HCO₃, and CO₃, and Cr(VI). In order to suit the groundwater for drinking and irrigation purposes, compared the value of selected parameters with the value of selected parameters from BIS drinking water quality standard and irrigation water quality indices. The physico-chemical study of the groundwater systems of selected sites of nearby places of Nagalkeni showed that the groundwater is nearly acidic and mostly oxidizing in nature. The results of the indices indicated that the groundwater samples in the study area found to be brackish water, results, groundwater from the study area is not suitable for irrigation purposes.

Keywords : Physico-Chemical Parameters, Tannery Industry Effluent, Groundwater Quality Indices

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014